

Establishing Guidelines for Program Evaluation for Community Health Initiatives

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: A community Program in Harlem created an assessment project to measure the impact of their community engagement efforts and procedures they have implemented. A suitable program evaluation is needed to review the internal processes of the initiative. The success of the assessment project will influence future work within the initiative.

Objectives: Successful community engagement involves preparation, training, and evaluation. The aim of this systematic literature review is to recommend the most beneficial program evaluation method for measuring engagement in community health initiatives.

Methods: Relevant articles were accessed through scholarly articles and databases, JSTOR, Google Scholar and Gale Research and appropriate keywords were queried. The reporting of this systematic review was guided by the standards of the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) Statement.

Results: The systematic review found several approaches useful for the program evaluation for a community health initiative. Among the relevant program evaluation methods are The Logic Model, RE-AIM framework, SMART criteria, Practical participation approach, concept mapping, The Community Engagement Toolkit, EQUIHP and SCORE. Based on the review these evaluations have the most beneficial methods to evaluate a community engagement program.

Conclusion: The recommendation is that Community Engagement programs use a mixed approach to evaluate the programs that they establish for underserved communities.

Keywords: program evaluation, community program assessment, program evaluation measurement, evaluating health promotion, culturally responsive evaluation, program evaluation methods.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

There is little consensus on which program evaluation is most appropriate for community engagement programs. This capstone's aim is to find the best evaluation method for community engagement programs. A successful program evaluation could improve community engagement programs in communities that are underserved and overlooked.

BACKGROUND/HEALTH STATUS OF POPULATION

Harlem is approximately 4.4 square miles and stretches for forty-five blocks from Central Park to 155th Street. These communities are comprised mostly of people of color who are of a lower socioeconomic status compared to their Manhattan counterparts. These neighborhoods are significantly disadvantaged, and medically and environmentally underserved. Neighborhoods with inhabitants of color often have less resources. Harlem had the higher infant mortality rates from 2018- 2020 compared to Manhattan with a rate of 5.6 per 1,000 births. Life expectancy during that time in Harlem was the lowest in Manhattan with 77.65 years. In 2020, premature deaths in Harlem were 405.6 per 100,000 compared to 59.7 in Greenwich Village and Soho.^{1,2}

DETERMINANTS OF HEALTH AND ILLNESS

The refusal of resources that support good health contributes to the differences in life expectancy in Harlem. Good health is not only determined by personal choices. Many other factors affect differences in health outcomes, including past and current discrimination.³ City of University of New York Graduate School of Public Health & Health Policy (CUNY SPH) started an initiative to improve the health and well-being of the Harlem community by assisting its existing community-based organizations. Among the support that is offered is communications, operational assistance, fundraising and training. Technical assistance is also provided through data management, research, and evaluation to selected organizations.

Community engagement organizations must engage in several activities to be successful. They must increase the community's knowledge of resources available to them. This may be done by doing community outreach events or social media communications. These communications must be done on a regular basis to ensure that the issues remain in the forefront of community conversation. Individuals within the community must build relationships outside the organization. This encourages the community not only to produce knowledge but to understand and apply knowledge to address and identify the relevant issues. When healthcare programs that are designed to improve outcomes are not steered by community interests and needs, the efforts remain detached from the people they propose to serve. This detachment restricts the impact and success of interventions, policies, and programs. Superficial engagement is not sufficient, the community must be given access to the decision-making process which leads to community

driven information, policies and eventually community change. Successful community engagement collaborates intimately with the community to identify their preferences and what degree of engagement is needed to effectively serve the needs of the population.^{4,5,6}

LITERATURE REVIEW OF NOTABLE PROGRAM EVALUATIONS

LOGIC MODEL

The literature review found several reliable methods of program evaluation that could be utilized to assess a community engagement program. The Logic Model is a detailed visualization of the relationship between a program's resources, activities, and its intended effect. Logic models first appeared in literature in the 1970s, showing how intervention influences behavior and attains objectives. The five key components of the Logic Model are inputs, activities, outputs, outcomes, and impacts. There are several advantages of creating and using logic models. Logic models communicate the program to people unfamiliar in a brief and compelling way. The visual tool helps program managers to gain insight into the program's processes and their own obligations to make it successful. The Logic Model focuses on long term goals which may not be suitable for community engagement which looks to implement changes in the short term.^{7,8}

REACH 2010 LOGIC MODEL

The REACH 2010 Logic Model evaluates community programs specifically in marginalized communities. The evaluation plan has three components: process evaluation, outcome evaluation and measuring performance. The process evaluation stage collects data to obtain insights about the actions of the program. During the outcome evaluation stage, surveillance data is used to determine the impact of the interventions that are executed. Measuring performance is a way to report responsibility or to gather evidence that helps participants understand how the program is working. The Logic model is suitable for the community engagement program evaluation because it is appropriate for comprehensive initiatives within communities. The visualization ranks features of the program that are most crucial for tracking and reporting, and it also helps recognize data needed for monitoring and improving the program.^{9,10,11}

RE-AIM

The RE-AIM (Reach, Effectiveness, Adoption, Implementation Maintenance) framework guides the planning and evaluation of a program. It addresses five areas of individual, organizational and multilevel outcomes essential to program impact and sustainability. Reach describes the number, ratio, and the appropriate characteristics of people who participate in each intervention

or program. Effectiveness is the impact of an intervention on significant outcomes and includes negative results, quality of life, and financial outcomes. Adoption is the number, ratio and the appropriate characteristics of the representatives who are initiating the intervention or program. Implementation refers to the representative's commitment to and the potential adjustments of an intervention and the correlated implementation plans which includes reliability of delivery as anticipated and the time and budget. Maintenance is the point to which a program or policy becomes established or part of the routine in policies and procedures of the organization.

The RE-AIM framework first appeared in literature in 2020 and addressed the known failures of translating scientific evidence into policy and practice. This method has been the most used framework in public health. Currently there are over seven hundred publications that use RE-AIM for planning and/or evaluation. This evaluation method is used most often because its tools can be used in various settings, diverse populations, and can evaluate specialized health issues. The RE-AIM framework does not require use of all stages in every evaluation. Community engagement programs would benefit from using this program evaluation because it is a viable choice for program evaluation framework in a real-world setting. It provides a format to thoroughly assess health program effects. The framework provides opportunities for modification at every step.^{12,13,14,15,16}

EQUIHP

The European Quality Instrument for Health Promotion (EQUIHP) tool is usually used to assess Health Promotion Programs for quality improvement or as a checklist for self-evaluation. It is separated into four components and reflects crucial factors for effective health promotion. This includes the structure of health promotion principles, project development and implementation, project management and sustainability. Some of the questions that are asked that pertain to the Community program engagement are: Does the project aim consider health inequalities and equity? Does the project address the issues of health in terms of the abilities and qualifications of people and/or the social and environmental conditions which affect health? This framework was first used at the end of the second year, well into the program's implementation. This is ideal for evaluation for programs that have existed for a period prior to the evaluation.^{17,18}

CONCEPT MAPPING

In the past 20 years concept mapping has been implemented in traditional measurement development and the evaluation processes. Concept mapping has been used to develop theory, plan for programs and social interventions and to evaluate social programs and develop measurements and scales. Concept mapping can be used to verify content validity, guide decision

making, combine perspectives and inform assessment. Trochim developed concept mapping in 1989 as a type of organized visual aid which can be used by researchers to develop a framework that can monitor evaluation and planning of programs. The review found several strengths to the application of the method. Researchers found it was a reliable method for establishing content validity and assisted the researcher with making assessment. They also found that it provided insight into the targeted population and provided a workable theory. Finally, it found that concept mapping provided an establishment for systematic and informative choices. Concept mapping can be useful in program evaluation for community engagement impact assessment because it can be used to identify the values of the program evaluation and can be utilized in a mixed methods evaluation model.^{19,20,21}

EFFICIENCY RESEARCH, EFFECTIVENESS RESEARCH, DISSEMINATION AND IMPLEMENTATION RESEARCH, PROCESS EVALUATION, SUMMATIVE EVALUATION

The review outlined the differing types of evaluation methods based on their design and purpose. The selection of the method is dependent on the focus of the initiative, the health issues, audience, and timeline. Efficiency research is an evaluation that is performed under strict and regulated conditions and commonly used under randomized controlled trials. Effectiveness research is performed under less controlled settings. This is used to assess if a random controlled trial is suitable for the program evaluation. Dissemination and implementation research uses evaluations used in real-world settings. This is useful in determining how to get the information out to those who would most benefit. This includes information about individual retention, establishing partnerships, data collection, sustainability, and scalability. Formative evaluation occurs during the initial stages of program implementation. It is used to run the initial stages of the program's initiatives to enhance the program's components. Process evaluation helps to define the parameters and addresses whether the intervention reached the appropriate audience and was implemented as intended. The most appropriate program evaluation for community impact assessment is summative evaluation. Summative evaluation reviews the accomplishment of the initiative's immediate impact as well as the intermediate and long-term outcomes. Summative evaluation also uses process evaluation since projected aims can only be reached if the intervention is delivered as intended.^{22,23,24,25,26,27,28}

COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT TOOLKIT

The Community Engagement toolkit would be a promising evaluation tool for the Community engagement impact assessment. The toolkit evaluates community programs' websites and web-based products based on the Community Engagement Toolkit specifically the user experience

evaluation (UXE). The Community Engagement toolkit was created by an instructor at a community college with expertise in community engagement. The evaluation is embedded into three of the four phases of the toolkit. The first phase is the usability inspection where researchers request feedback on the user's experiences navigating the website. The feedback enabled the researchers to update the layout of the website. The purpose of the usability study phase is to collect more detailed feedback. This phase focuses primarily on the design, ease of learning, efficacy of use, and satisfaction with the user interface. The final phase is the utility study. This phase evaluates the usefulness and the content associated with the website. During this stage users are asked to rate if the features of the website were appropriate for the intervention. The research showed that technology can be used to build useful evaluation that engages community participants in the evaluation process.^{29,30,31}

FORMATIVE EVALUATION

Formative evaluation comes from a belief that the program will be improved by the assessment, although there is little practical evidence that this is true. There are two important components done during formative evaluation. Once the key findings of the formative evaluation are presented it is determined how these findings influenced the final program and the summative evaluation. Formative evaluation can strengthen some components of a program. It can find negative feedback about program components which can be translated into program improvements. Although there is little empirical evidence that this would be an effective program evaluation on its own, it can be used along with another program evaluation method such as summative evaluation to get the most beneficial outcome.^{32,33,34}

CIPP

CIPP was developed to assess techniques that have influenced the development of common educational evaluation models. These theories are used to inform educational program evaluation models but can certainly be translated as a program evaluation method for the community engagement assessment. These techniques support learning about the processes within the programs which allow for increased program improvement. The CIPP (context/input/process/product) model focuses on overall program improvement instead of improving on one element of the program. The CIPP model contains several corresponding sets of evaluation studies that allow assessors to consider program information that may have been overlooked. During the context evaluation stage, the researcher can choose the most appropriate data collection method by gathering documents, conducting interviews, or creating surveys. It is at the product evaluation stage that researchers may do a literature review or consult experts in the field. Overall, this approach appears to be very compatible with the needs of a community engagement assessment initiative.^{35,36}

REALIST APPROACH

Because public health interventions are complicated, evaluation requires studying the program components and their interaction with open social systems. The realist approach helps the evaluators to understand how the program relates to both individuals involved and the circumstances in which it is applied, with the goal of improving population health and lowering social disparities in health. This approach focuses on the relationship between perspectives, mechanisms, and outcomes. A mechanism is unseen but tangible. It is an element of interpretation and feedback regarding the resources available. Community engagement programs are developed with a realist approach in mind, as they evaluate several community and social factors affecting the community. For further program evaluation the realist approach would be beneficial for program evaluation for underserved communities. I would recommend this program evaluation however, evaluators must first agree on a precise definition of the mechanism beforehand so there is a consensus.^{37,38,39,40}

COMPLEX SYSTEMS METHODS

Evaluating programs from a complex system perspective can help researchers produce evidence that better interprets the complexity of real-world settings. This may increase the relevance and proof of the data to better improve health and decrease health inequalities. The research attempted to identify the complex systems and the methods in which the evaluation can be applied to public health and examined the evidence generated by the different methods. The research collaborated with experts in the field and searched electronic databases such as MEDLINE, Scopus, and Web of Science. The researchers developed a framework based on the review with five stages. Theorizing can classify points of intervention and indicate ways in which it could interact with that system. Predictions are used to replicate the effects of interventions that are yet to be implemented. This process would be useful in community engagement assessment. Using complex systems methods can be applied, revised, or merged to produce several types of evaluative evidence.^{41,42,43.}

DATA EVALUATION

I created a chart of the evaluation methods I reviewed and how many times they appeared in Academia/Medical Education, Government, Healthcare and Community Engagement Assessment. Academia/Medical Education is defined as a university or a medical school. Government use of program evaluation methods is defined as city, state, federal and international governments. Healthcare entities include medical groups, physicians, and hospitals. Finally, Community groups are defined as a community organization, registered charity organization, or a non-profit community group. Each category was queried in the research tool 'Research Rabbit.' The words program evaluation' was added to each below framework. For example, RE-AIM is

listed in the below chart. I searched for “RE-AIM program evaluation” and viewed all articles to identify the environment in which the research article was written.

TABLE 1.0

Evaluation Framework	Academic/Medical Education	Government	Healthcare	Community Groups
CIPP	15	2	33	0
Community Engagement Toolkit	0	0	7	43
Complex Systems Methods	4	1	45	0
Concept Mapping	23	6	18	3
Dissemination Research	16	3	29	2
Effectiveness Research	21	2	24	3
Efficiency Research	21	7	22	0
EQUIHP	2	23	16	9
Formative Evaluation	3	9	23	15
Logic Model	25	1	20	4
Process Evaluation	23	5	14	8
RE-AIM	3	2	43	2
Realist Approach	2	2	40	6
Summative Evaluation	20	5	24	1

The bar chart shows that most of the frameworks were assessed within healthcare settings and secondly, academic, and medical education settings. Program evaluation has not been significantly assessed in community group settings besides the aptly named Community Engagement Toolkit.

CHART 1.0

The extensive article review found twenty-two key concepts that were consistent throughout each paper. Below is a chart of important concepts in program evaluation, their descriptions, and some examples of how they involve program evaluation.

TABLE 2.0

CONCEPT	DESCRIPTION	EXAMPLE
<i>Accuracy</i>	<i>Standards that ensure that findings are believed to be correct</i>	<i>Documentation, Quantitative information analysis, Qualitative information analysis</i>
Activities	Steps taken before actual program evaluation is done	Holding meetings or events, conducting training of staff
Data Analysis	Techniques used to analyze information	Summarizing, translating, and disseminating the data obtained from the program evaluation
Effectiveness	Assessment of program evaluation impacts	The intensity in program activities yield the desired effects
External validity	Generalization of program evaluation results	Can the program evaluation be used in other environments
<i>Feasibility</i>	<i>Standard for good evaluation</i>	<i>Cost effectiveness, Procedural practicality, Political sustainability</i>
Framework	Steps in the program evaluation framework, program activities within the program evaluation	Choosing a relevant program evaluation, outlining program descriptions, assessing stakeholder engagement, gathering relevant evidence, and justifying the findings
Impacts	Assessing the difference between the expected outcomes of a program evaluation and the actual conclusions	The observed results, encouraging and discouraging, planned, and unplanned, direct, and indirect
Implementation	The execution of the program evaluation.	Defining the goals, researching, assigning responsibilities, confirming

		plans, and allocating resources
Internal validity	Relates to the results of the program evaluation	Are claims about the attributes or efficiency of a program is accurate
Objectives	Goals of the program evaluation	Perceived results of the program evaluation
Outcomes	Short- and long-term changes that will result from the program evaluation.	Actual outcomes of the program evaluation.
Outputs	Detectible results produced by program activities	Direct results of activities leading to increase knowledge of program or program improvements
Participation/Partnerships	People contributing to the program evaluation	Number of participants, characteristics of people contributing to program evaluation.
Planning	Actions and strategies that take place during the program evaluation	Objectives and goals
<i>Propriety</i>	<i>Standard for good evaluation</i>	<i>Assures evaluation is ethical and considers the interests of all who participates in the program evaluation</i>
<i>Program Environment</i>	<i>Environment in which the evaluation is taking place</i>	<i>Evaluations can take place in academia, government, or community engagement.</i>
Resources	Assets used to develop program evaluation	Financial resources, equipment such as computers, cellphones or software, facilities, and staff
Stakeholders	Groups and/or individuals with interests in the program evaluation	Community members, Staff, Researchers
Survey	Tool used to gather data using questions from a sample population with the intent of	Qualtrics, Google Forms

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	understanding the entire population.	
Sustainability	<i>The ability to maintain or support program evaluation continuously in the short and long term.</i>	<i>Can the program evaluation be used in future iterations with modification?</i>
Utility	Standard for a good evaluation	Identifying stakeholders, credibility of evaluator, impact of evaluation

I created a decision tree using Visio, to determine the most effective method to use for community engagement program evaluation. The decision tree uses the key concepts highlighted on the prior table. There are certain standards in good evaluation. A good evaluation factors in Accuracy, Feasibility and Propriety. I also added Program Environment and Sustainability to this level because I found these concepts to be useful in choosing an appropriate program evaluation. These frameworks are on the square boxes on the top level of the tree.

Accuracy: Accuracy standards safeguard that the evaluation findings are correct.

Does the program evaluation use quantitative and qualitative sources?

Quantitative data consists of information obtained by survey or a random control trial. Qualitative data collects information from already organized information such as research papers and statistics. It is important to have several sources of information that can confirm the same evidence independently.

Has the program evaluation been systematically reviewed?

Evidence that program evaluation was successful in the past is important. The systematic review found that several program evaluations have been assessed successfully. Having an already established blueprint in program evaluation helps researchers not make the mistakes that previous researchers did.

Feasibility: Feasibility is the state or intensity that the evaluation can be done conveniently.

Does the program evaluation make sense?

This question evaluates if the program evaluation's tools and mechanisms are compatible with the type of program that is being evaluated.

Is the program evaluation practical?

Is the program evaluation straightforward? Can it be implemented in the allotted time?

Does the program evaluation have political practicality?

Is the program evaluation relevant to the political climate? This question is important because it asks whether the program evaluation meets the needs of the public.

Is the program evaluation cost effective?

Due to limited resources the program evaluation must make the most of its limited resources.

Propriety: Assures evaluation is ethical and considers the interests of all who participate in the program evaluation.

Is the program evaluation ethical? Would participants have any conflicts of interest? Does it serve the needs of the population? Does the program evaluation respect the rights of the participants? Is it fiscally responsible?

Program evaluation must adhere to several standards of behavior and morals. This includes respecting and protecting the rights of human subjects. Researchers must assign responsibilities

in the evaluation, what needs to be done, how it needs to be done and by whom and within what time. Potential conflicts of interest must be communicated to ensure the procedures and conclusions are not compromised. Finally, results of the evaluation must be accessible to everyone involved in the evaluation process.

Program environment

Is the program evaluation relevant to the program environment?

This is the environment in which the evaluation is taking place. The review found program evaluation methods used in academia, city, and federal governments. Overall, these program evaluation methods were suitable for community engagement assessment.

Based on Chart 1.0 and Bar Chart 1.0. The most appropriate program evaluations for Community Engagement Assessment are Community Engagement Toolkit, Concept Mapping, EQUIHP, Formative evaluation and Process Evaluation which appears on the second level of the chart.

Sustainability:

Can the program evaluation be used in future iteration with modifications?

Sustainability is the capacity to maintain or support program evaluation continuously in the short and long term. The sustainability of the program evaluation is why a mixed methods approach would be the best method to use in community engagement assessment.

On the second level of the decision tree, I placed all the suitable programs in rectangles with connector lines to the above standards of good program evaluation. As you can see by the connectors, many programs have the qualities that would make program evaluation successful. The third level of the chart asks the defining question. Can the program evaluation be used in other evaluations? This is where I got the idea to use a mixed methods program evaluation framework for community engagement assessment.

MIXED METHODS APPROACH

There are many approaches that can be used as a method to evaluate the programs affiliated with community engagement. I would recommend community engagement programs use a mixed methods approach. The mixed methods approach is not a new concept but has become common in evaluating outcomes in health care program policy effectiveness and implementation. The mixed methods approach involves using several program methods to form a suitable program evaluation. A mixed-method evaluation thoroughly integrates two or more evaluation methods, during each evaluation process and it draws on both quantitative and qualitative information.^{44,45}

A mixed methods approach has been used to achieve different purposes. Five distinct functions were identified in the review. Convergence is where one type of data is used to confirm conclusions reached from evaluation from another type of data, this is also known as triangulation. Triangulation is a comparative analysis which allows the evaluator to catch and validate complex findings. It can provide complete insight from a range of views of the services and policies of a program. This is where qualitative data is transformed or quantified. Quantitative data is used to estimate outcomes while qualitative data is used to evaluate process. This function is known as complementarity, it is also where qualitative methods are used to provide complex understanding of the data and where quantitative methods are used to provide breadth of understanding of the data. The third function is expansion or explanation, it is where qualitative methods are used to expand on the conclusions of the quantitative data. During development, evaluation methods such as concept mapping can be used to create ideas, devices or interventions that can be used in other methods, such as the logic model to answer other questions. The final function, sampling, is simply using one method to find a sample of participants for use with another method.^{46,47,48.}

Researchers have several options if they decide to use a mixed methods approach for the most effective evaluation design. In parallel combinations, each method is performed completely and separately from other methods. Methods are used individually, and the findings are combined after the data is collected. Multiple methods also can be used at separate times and in a specific order. With sequential combinations, methods are used one after the other, with the conclusions from methods used prior in the evaluation advising the design and execution of methods used afterwards. Parallel or sequential processes, or both depending on the direction of the project and the purpose of the evaluation can be combined as a multi-level mixed method evaluation.^{49,50}

A mixed methods approach will incorporate different collection techniques such as observations, surveys, secondary data reviews such as reviewing literature and reviewing prior systems evaluations in similar programs. There are benefits to using mixed methods approach in program evaluation. Using a mixed method approach is more likely to reveal results that were not predicted. It can provide a deeper understanding of why internal policies are not effective and captures a variety of views that might not be obtained by one method. The mixed method approach can be used when evaluation questions demand different methods or when a single evaluation question requires more than one process to answer all sections. It can be used to increase confidence in the evaluation results. Lastly, the results from one method used in the mixed methods approach can help inform future phases of evaluation.⁵¹

RECOMMENDATIONS

The multi-level combination method would be the most appropriate program evaluation for community engagement assessment. To evaluate if the program is effective, it will require information from distinct levels. The multi-level method uses both quantitative and qualitative processes which are combined at distinct levels of the evaluation, it uses at least two data sources to answer correlated questions. This method is particularly helpful for service delivery evaluation. Community engagement assessment requires feedback from a variety of stakeholders. This includes the affected community, community partnership organizations and students and faculty at the academic institution.

Multi-level combinations are illustrated in the below chart. Different data collection methods can happen simultaneously or sequentially. Each group will be managed in different rounds and separated based on the nature of the questions.

TABLE 3.0

The below table is a sample of a mixed method evaluation design, these are evaluation steps I recommend for community engagement assessment.

TABLE 4.0

Data collection method	Data collection instrument	Data source
Internal Review	Annotated bibliography	Student Interns/Project Staff Managers
Review of Community Statistics	New York City Department of Health Data, Harlem Community Board Data, US Census Data	Student Interns/Project Staff Managers
Focus group interview	Community Members	Residents of Harlem
Focus group interview	Community Partnership organizations	Community organizations
Focus group interview	Students Faculty	Graduate Students, Employees of School
Survey	Qualtrics, Google Forms	Residents of Harlem, Community Organizations, Graduate Students, Employees of School

The fieldwork for this capstone required students to do an annotated bibliography of the best evaluation methods for community engagement. This was completed by two graduate students and was reviewed by program managers at the community engagement program. My recommendations would be to review community statistics from the New York Department of Health, US Census Bureau Data and Harlem Community Board 9, 10 and 11. The data should include Health statistics from the NYC Department of Health, demographic information from the US Census Bureau and the Community boards. This information would help to develop questions based on the needs of the population. I suggest three separate focus group interviews for Community members, Community Partnership organizations and Students and Faculty of the graduate school. The final recommendation for program evaluation would be an online survey tool for each group to complete. The questions on the survey would be tailored to each of the segments of participants.

LIMITATIONS

I am recommending the Mixed method program evaluation for assessing community engagement in communities that are underserved but this approach is not without its drawbacks. This approach requires the evaluators to have a distinct set of skills in investigation and interpretation and that they use the appropriate research systems. Each method has its own disadvantages and combining several may lead to heightened intensity which will prolong the program evaluation

process. The mixed method program evaluation may require more adaptation than using one method, this also may increase the time it takes to complete the evaluation and will require more program resources. Both quantitative and qualitative methods pull significant evaluation resources. Budgeting for additional resources, such as staff and equipment, must be taken into consideration when employing this method of program evaluation.

CONCLUSION

The suggested program evaluation for community engagement assessment is a mixed method approach. The actual program evaluation that was used for this community engagement assessment is outlined in Table 4.0. The project decided to complete the surveys before the focus group interviews.

The future of mixed methods research should build on what has been learned in the chosen personalized program evaluation and replicating the frameworks that produce the most effective outcomes. The future of program evaluation should include software development tools to assist with the execution of the mixed methods evaluation design. These tools can be used to collect data, perform data analysis, and assist with dissemination of findings.

Program evaluation designs and their discoveries will steer the strategy, execution, and evaluation of future community engagement assessment. Successful program evaluation will ultimately strengthen the relationships between stakeholders and improve the quality of life and health outcomes in underserved communities.

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